

Is the universe a product of our imagination? A brief essay on the intersection between mathematics and physics

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ABSTRACT

This essay explores the intersection between Mathematics and Physics, proposing a reflection on possible conceptual connections between elegant mathematical structures and fundamental constants of nature. Starting from Euler's identity, renowned for its beauty and synthesis of different branches of Mathematics, the study examines relationships involving the speed of light and the gravitational coupling constant between electrons. The approach adopts a physico-philosophical perspective, suggesting that the microscopic scale can serve as a convergence point between mathematical idealization and the imprecision of the physical world. Drawing on Platonic and Kantian ideas, the essay emphasizes that knowledge of the universe is not merely a passive discovery but also a construction of the human mind: the representation of space, time, and physical constants depends on conceptual structures that shape our experience. In this sense, Mathematics provides symbolic and metaphorical tools to understand fundamental aspects of reality, while Physics offers empirical data that guide and constrain these abstractions. The article does not propose a new physical theory but encourages reflection on the role of scientific imagination, mathematical abstraction, and empirical observation in building models that articulate the ideal world and the sensible world.

Keywords: Physics Education. Mathematics Education. Euler's identity. Fundamental constants. Philosophy of science.

1. INTRODUCTION

Although many consider philosophy irrelevant to physics, Rovelli (2018) argues that it exerts a profound and continuous influence on the development of science, contributing to reflection on methods and theoretical assumptions. Indeed, since the beginnings of physics, great scientists have engaged not only with experiments and equations but also with deep philosophical meditations on Nature. These reflections, often arising from the confrontation between theory and experience, reveal the human effort to understand reality in a broader way than numbers alone can express ^[1].

In the 20th century, the advent of quantum mechanics brought a true reality shock, challenging classical intuitions about determinism, causality, and objectivity. Physicists such as Einstein, Bohr, and Schrödinger expressed, at different times, their perplexities and philosophical concerns regarding the behavior of the subatomic world, demonstrating that the theory not only describes phenomena but also confronts our most fundamental conceptions of Nature ^[2].

Despite the extraordinary success of quantum mechanics, a profound conceptual mismatch remains between quantum theory and general relativity, a difficulty that goes beyond technical obstacles. It is not merely a matter of developing compatible equations, but also of metaphysically rethinking the nature of spacetime, the ultimate structure of reality, and the limits of our knowledge ^[3]. Quantum mechanics and general relativity may require a relational ontology: fundamental objects would not possess intrinsic identity, but would exist through structural relations, which are qualitatively distinct in the quantum case (entanglement) and in the gravitational case (metric relations) ^[3].

In this context, it is possible to draw parallels with Plato's world of ideas, in which the sensible reality is merely a shadow of perfect and immutable forms ^[4]. Just as Plato postulated that true knowledge requires the contemplation of ideas ^[4], the philosophical reflections of physicists can be seen as attempts to attain a deeper and more abstract understanding of reality, one that transcends immediate experience and experimental measurements ^[5].

Therefore, studying the philosophical reflections of both contemporary and historical physicists not only illuminates the trajectory of science but also provides conceptual tools to tackle the persistent enigmas of Nature, the quantum world, and gravity.

In light of these conceptual challenges, the opportunity arises to explore, in a reflective and theoretical manner, how certain elegant mathematical structures can provide metaphors or points of convergence with the fundamental constants and laws of physics, without the intention of proposing a testable physical theory.

This article proposes a theoretical essay on a possible connection between one of the most elegant and fundamental equations in Mathematics, Euler's identity, and certain relationships in Physics, such as the expression of the speed of light in terms of electromagnetic constants and the gravitational coupling constant between two electrons. The approach adopts a physico-philosophical perspective, suggesting that the microscopic scale could represent a convergence point between mathematical idealization and the imprecision of the physical world, revisiting Platonic ideas

regarding the coexistence of the world of ideas and the sensible world. It is emphasized that the article does not aim to propose a unification theory, but rather to present an essay on a possible cognitive extrapolation between the domains of Mathematics and Physics. This extrapolation allows for a more integrated visualization in the teaching of these two disciplines.

2. EULER'S IDENTITY

Euler's identity is considered one of the most beautiful expressions in mathematics because it condenses, in a single surprisingly simple equality, fundamental ideas from different areas of knowledge, and is written as:

$$e^{i\pi} + 1 = 0 \quad (1)$$

In this way, it connects the number e , associated with continuous growth processes and analysis; the number π , which naturally arises in the geometry of circles and in periodic phenomena; and the imaginary unit i , which extends the number system and makes a full understanding of complex numbers possible. The fact that these elements, each with such distinct origins and meanings, appear together in the operation of exponentiation and yet result exactly in -1 , so that their sum with 1 produces zero, is seen as an extraordinary synthesis [6].

It is worth noting that the development of the number zero, especially in India, was fundamental for the creation of an efficient positional numeral system, allowing any quantity to be represented with just ten symbols. This innovation enabled a numerical system far more practical and powerful than the classical Roman or Greek systems, which lacked a functional zero and positional notation [7]. Thus, paradoxically, zero represents “nothing” while allowing the largest quantities to be represented in a more compact and simple way, effectively “representing” the “whole” of countable objects.

The beauty of the equation lies precisely in this unexpected convergence: concepts belonging to different fields, such as analysis, geometry, and algebra, come together elegantly and precisely, revealing mathematics' ability to unify profound ideas in a concise and intellectually harmonious expression [6]. Moreover, this compact structure synthesizes deep properties of analysis, trigonometry, and complex arithmetic, making it an object of mathematical and cultural fascination [8,9].

Historically, the identity is a particular case of Euler's formula [10],

$$e^{i\theta} = \cos \theta + i \sin \theta, \quad (2)$$

which was published in the treatise *Introductio in Analysin Infinitorum* [11], a central work for the development of analysis in the 18th century [6,12]. Although Euler never explicitly wrote the identity $e^{i\pi} = -1$, his general formulation of the complex exponential makes this result immediate, which is why the identity is traditionally attributed to him [6,12].

The development of this formula is the result of a long historical process, beginning with John Napier's logarithms and further advanced by Leibniz, Johann Bernoulli, and Roger Cotes, who studied logarithms of complex numbers and obtained equivalent expressions, such as

$$\ln (\cos \theta + i \sin \theta) = i \theta \quad (3)$$

although without arriving at the complete exponential form ^[6,13]. Bernoulli also contributed by investigating areas of circular sectors and discussing the value of $\ln (-1)$, enabling Euler to identify that $\ln (-1) = i\pi$, a relationship essential for the identity ^[13,14].

Thus, Euler's identity not only represents a particular case of the complex exponential, but also synthesizes centuries of mathematical development and remains a symbol of the harmony between different branches of mathematics: algebra, analysis, trigonometry, and complex numbers.

3. THE SPEED OF LIGHT

The formulation of Maxwell's equations in the 19th century represented one of the greatest milestones in theoretical physics, unifying electrical, magnetic, and optical phenomena within a single conceptual framework. This synthesis revealed that light is a manifestation of the electromagnetic field, propagating according to universal laws that describe both radiation and the fundamental interactions of charged matter ^[15].

Over more than a century and a half, Maxwell's legacy has extended beyond the purely theoretical domain. His equations became the foundation for technological innovations ranging from antennas and waveguides to optical fibers, metamaterials, and modern communication systems. With advances in nanoscience and materials engineering, it has become possible to manipulate electromagnetic waves at previously unimaginable scales, giving rise to devices capable of controlling, concentrating, and even precisely redirecting light ^[15].

Considering the differential form of Maxwell's Equations applied to a vacuum, without electric charges and without electric currents, the following relations can be obtained ^[16-18]:

$$\vec{\nabla} \cdot \vec{E} = 0 \quad (\text{Gauss's Law for Electrostatics}) \quad (4)$$

$$\vec{\nabla} \cdot \vec{B} = 0 \quad (\text{Gauss's Law for Magnetism}) \quad (5)$$

$$\vec{\nabla} \times \vec{E} = -\frac{\partial \vec{B}}{\partial t} \quad (\text{Faraday's Law}) \quad (6)$$

$$\vec{\nabla} \times \vec{B} = \mu_0 \cdot \varepsilon_0 \frac{\partial \vec{E}}{\partial t} \quad (\text{Ampère's Law with Maxwell's Correction}) \quad (7)$$

Where $\vec{\nabla}$ is the differential nabla operator, \vec{E} is the electric field vector, \vec{B} is the magnetic field vector, ε_0 is the electric permittivity of vacuum, ρ is the volumetric electric charge density within the volume enclosed by the Gaussian surface on which the electric field (\vec{E}) is analyzed, t is time, μ_0 is the magnetic permeability of vacuum, and \vec{J} is the electric current density vector. Through some manipulations, the following relations can be obtained ^[18]:

$$\nabla^2 \vec{E} = \mu_0 \cdot \varepsilon_0 \frac{\partial^2 \vec{E}}{\partial t^2} \quad (8)$$

$$\nabla^2 \vec{B} = \mu_0 \cdot \varepsilon_0 \frac{\partial^2 \vec{B}}{\partial t^2} \quad (9)$$

Equations (8) and (9) satisfy the equation for a three-dimensional wave ^[18,19]:

$$\nabla^2 f(x, y, z) = \frac{1}{v^2} \frac{\partial^2 f(x, y, z)}{\partial t^2} \quad (10)$$

suggesting the propagation of a wave of a new nature, called an electromagnetic wave, composed of the joint and perpendicular oscillation of the electric (\vec{E}) and magnetic (\vec{B}) fields. It is worth noting that Equation (10) was initially deduced from the propagation of waves in material media, such as strings or fluids, serving as a basis for understanding more general wave phenomena. For example, it can be derived for a pulse on a string following Newton's laws (one-dimensional model) or for waves in a three-dimensional medium ^[19]. By comparing Equations ((8), ((9) and ((10), it can be concluded that empty space allows the propagation of electromagnetic waves with speed c , which is the speed of light itself, and whose relationship is given by:

$$v = c = \frac{1}{\sqrt{\mu_0 \cdot \varepsilon_0}} \quad (11)$$

From this relationship, the following manipulation can be performed:

$$1 = c \cdot \sqrt{\mu_0 \cdot \varepsilon_0} \quad (12)$$

Which, in turn, is a pure number without any unit of measurement—an equality that will be used in the following sections.

4. THE GRAVITATIONAL COUPLING FACTOR

The fine-structure constant, usually denoted by α , is one of the fundamental quantities in modern physics. Its name has historical origins, having been introduced by Arnold Sommerfeld as a measure of the relative order of magnitude of the splitting, called fine structure, of the degenerate levels of the Bohr atom, arising from relativistic effects ^[20,21]. The constant can be expressed as ^[22]:

$$\alpha = \frac{e^2}{4 \cdot \pi \cdot \varepsilon_0 \cdot \hbar \cdot c} \cong \frac{1}{137,036} \quad (13)$$

Where e is the elementary charge of the electron, ε_0 is the electric permittivity of vacuum, \hbar is the reduced Planck constant, and c is the speed of light. This constant is often referred to simply by its approximate value, $1 / 137$, a number that, over time, has acquired an almost mystical aura due to its enigmatic presence in the laws of nature ^[23].

From its formulation, it has been observed that α is closely related to the elementary electric charge e and can even be interpreted as a way of expressing the numerical value of this charge in a

dimensionless form, since the constants h , c , and ε_0 are known with high precision and define the reference units of the International System [21].

Although the original meaning of the constant was linked to the splitting of atomic energy levels, its importance has transcended this historical context. Today, α is recognized as a fundamental parameter that permeates all physical scales in which the electromagnetic interaction plays an essential role: from systems of elementary particles to macroscopic phenomena. This ubiquity allows its value to be determined through various independent experimental methods, reflecting its unifying role and its metrological precision within contemporary physics [21].

Another dimensionless constant associated with gravity can also be defined. This is the gravitational coupling constant (α_G), widely discussed in various theoretical physics works [24-31]. This constant, usually denoted by α_G , is defined as the ratio between the gravitational attractive force between two electrons and the Coulomb force [30] between two Planck charges, and is generally expressed as follows [31]:

$$\alpha_G = \frac{G \cdot \frac{m_e^2}{R^2}}{\frac{1}{4 \cdot \pi \cdot \varepsilon_0 \cdot \hbar \cdot c} \cdot \frac{e^2}{R^2}} = \frac{G \cdot m_e^2}{\hbar \cdot c} = \left(\frac{m_e}{m_p}\right)^2 = 1,7518 \cdot 10^{-45} \quad (14)$$

Where G is the universal gravitational constant, m_e is the mass of the electron, m_p is the Planck mass, R is a hypothetical distance between two electrons, ε_0 is the electric permittivity, \hbar is the reduced Planck constant, c is the speed of light, and e is the elementary charge of the electron. In the present work, for the following sections, the following relation will be used:

$$\alpha_G = \frac{G \cdot m_e^2}{\hbar \cdot c} = 1,7518 \cdot 10^{-45} \quad (15)$$

The choice of the electron and its properties for the calculation is justified by the fact that it is the elementary particle with the smallest known electric charge-to-mass ratio [32,33], in addition to playing a fundamental role in a wide range of physical [18,22,33] and chemical [34] interactions.

5. INTERSECTION BETWEEN MATHEMATICS AND PHYSICS

Euler's identity (Equation ((1))), the definition of the speed of light (Equation ((11))), and the gravitational coupling constant (Equation ((15))) can be used in an attempt to connect the world of Mathematics with the world of Physics. By substituting the equality from Equation ((12)) into Equation ((1)):

$$e^{i\pi} + c \cdot \sqrt{\mu_0 \cdot \varepsilon_0} = 0 \quad (16)$$

Considering that the largest numerical reference is the value 1, according to Equation ((14)), it is observed that the value 10^{-45} in the same equation is 10^{45} times smaller than 1. Such a discrepancy allows it to be approximated to zero. However, it is important to distinguish the mathematical zero, an abstract and absolute concept representing numerical nonexistence [35], from the physical zero, which corresponds to an extremely small magnitude, but not necessarily null in the

real world ^[36]. While the mathematical zero is an exact entity ^[35], the physical zero is always an approximation, dependent on scale, units, and experimental precision ^[36]. This distinction suggests that, although we may treat $\alpha_G \approx 0$ to simplify formal relations, it still possesses physical significance, even if imperceptible in practice. Such reflection reinforces the idea that certain mathematical concepts, when applied to physics, must be interpreted with care, as abstract idealization does not always coincide with measurable reality, and mathematical approximations can obscure fundamental nuances of the physical universe.

One of the largest interferometers in the world, Advanced LIGO, exhibits high precision, such that small variations in the lengths of the interferometer arms, on the order of femtometers to picometers, can be detected. This sensitivity, expressed in strain — the relative variation of the interferometer arm lengths — of about 10^{-23} to $10^{-24} \text{ Hz}^{-1/2}$ in the 100 Hz range, allows the observation of compact binary systems at cosmological distances ^[37]. Even considering this extraordinary sensitivity, the proposed gravitational coupling constant α_G is extremely small, far below the minimum variation detectable by LIGO. This justifies, for practical purposes, approximating it as zero in the current analyses, without compromising consistency with experimental measurements.

In this way, the following relation can be constructed:

$$\alpha_G = \frac{G \cdot m_e^2}{\hbar \cdot c} = 1,7518 \cdot 10^{-45} \approx 0 \quad (17)$$

Thus, the approximation (Equation (17)) is used in Equation ((16)):

$$e^{i\pi} + c \cdot \sqrt{\mu_0 \cdot \varepsilon_0} \approx \frac{G \cdot m_e^2}{\hbar \cdot c} \quad (18)$$

By manipulating the previous equation and isolating the complex number i , we have:

$$i \approx \frac{1}{\pi} \ln \left(\frac{G \cdot m_e^2}{\hbar \cdot c} - c \cdot \sqrt{\mu_0 \cdot \varepsilon_0} \right) \quad (19)$$

The proposed Equation (19) suggests an attempt to unify, in a single dimensionless and complex expression, fundamental quantities from gravitation, quantum mechanics, and electromagnetism. The fact that the term i , which refers to the imaginary domain and, symbolically, to the unobservable or abstract aspect of reality, is associated with the logarithm of a combination of these constants can be interpreted as a mathematical metaphor for the coexistence between the ideal world, represented by Mathematics, and the physical world. Thus, the relation expresses not only a curious formal equivalence between fundamental dimensions of nature, but also a conceptual indication that unity among the different domains of Physics may reside in mathematical structures not yet fully understood.

6. IS THE UNIVERSE A PRODUCT OF OUR IMAGINATION

The deduced Equation (19) can be seen not only as a mathematical construction but also as a metaphor for the way human thought attempts to unify the real and the abstract. The imaginary term i symbolizes the domain of thought and idealization — that which is not directly observable, but structures our theories and conceptions of the world. Meanwhile, the physical terms G , m , \hbar , c , μ_0 , and ϵ_0 represent materiality, the fundamental constants that describe the measurable behavior of the universe.

It is interesting to note that the related fundamental physical constants (G , m , \hbar , c , μ_0 and ϵ_0) act as a bridge between the macroscopic and microscopic worlds, connecting seemingly distant scales within a single formulation. In Equation (19), this connection becomes even more evident with the presence of the imaginary number i , which represents the dimension of human thought and idealization. In this way, the equation not only describes measurable relations but also highlights how scientific knowledge arises from the interaction between the observable and the conceivable, between the physical and the imaginary.

From this perspective, it can be interpreted that the universe, as we understand it, is a product of the interaction between our imagination and the regularities we observe. The very representation of matter, whether on a macroscopic or microscopic scale, is ultimately imaginary. We create models and mathematical symbols to represent a reality that may exist only as a conceptual projection of the human mind. Thus, the physical universe would not be an autonomous and independent object of consciousness, but a reflection of the ways in which we organize and interpret experience.

In other words, the “real” emerges as a symbolic construction of reason. The boundary between the physical and the imaginary dissolves, and the universe becomes, in this sense, the most sophisticated product of human scientific imagination.

From the Kantian perspective, the universe as we know it is not something directly accessible, but rather constructed by our cognition through categories of understanding and sensible intuition ^[38]. In this sense, Equation (19) can be seen not only as a mathematical construction, but also as a metaphor for the way human thought organizes and interprets reality. The imaginary number i symbolizes the domain of idealization — that which is not directly observable, but structures our theories — while the physical terms G , m , \hbar , c , μ_0 , and ϵ_0 represent the measurable regularities of the universe. Thus, the physical universe, ultimately, does not present itself as an autonomous object, but as a product of the interaction between our cognition and observable phenomena. The “real” reality emerges as a symbolic construction of reason, dissolving the boundary between the physical and the imaginary, and reinforcing the idea that scientific knowledge is simultaneously a discovery and a creation of the human mind.

Within the scientific community, various approaches have sought to formulate dimensionless relations that unify the fundamental constants of nature ^[39-41]. Among these attempts, the proposals by Pellis in *Dimensionless Theory of Everything* ^[39] and *Euler’s Identity in the Unification of the Fundamental Interactions* ^[40] stand out, exploring the possibility of expressing fundamental

interactions through pure mathematical combinations and universal symmetries. Although these studies are primarily theoretical and exploratory in nature, they reinforce the idea that true physical unification may emerge from dimensionless mathematical relations. In this context, the present proposal is presented as a more restricted and dimensionally coherent formulation, maintaining the spirit of dimensionless unification while seeking a conceptually more grounded approach that is compatible with the principles of contemporary physics.

7. CONCLUSION

The reflection developed here sought to explore, in a conceptual and non-dogmatic way, possible approximations between elegant mathematical structures and certain fundamental parameters of physics. By linking Euler's identity, the expression for the speed of light, and the gravitational coupling constant between electrons, the goal was not to propose a unifying theory, but to highlight how different domains of knowledge — the abstract and the empirical — can illuminate each other when observed from a philosophical perspective.

The dimensionless relations discussed, although mathematically simple, serve as an invitation to contemplation: they show that physics, even in its most technical aspects, remains permeated by idealizations, analogies, and representations that ultimately depend on human imagination. The distinction between mathematical zero and physical zero, the role of approximations, and the symbolic character of the imaginary number reinforce that theoretical construction is not a perfect mirror of reality, but an active interpretation—a way to organize experience within conceptual forms that make sense to us.

In the end, the essay suggests that the universe, as we describe it, is inseparable from the mental models we use to understand it. Mathematics provides the structures, physics provides the regularities arising from observations of nature, and imagination acts as a bridge between the two. The derived equation, far from having literal physical meaning, functions as a metaphor for this deep interaction between abstraction and observation. Thus, the text reiterates that scientific laws are not only discoveries but also inventions in the noblest sense: forms created by the human mind to give coherence to the world.

From the perspective of physics education, the approach presented can be used as a teaching resource to discuss with students the difference between mathematical idealization and physical reality, the role of approximations, and the meaning of dimensionless quantities. Euler's identity, often presented merely as a mathematical curiosity, can serve as a starting point for reflections on the construction of physical models, stimulating a more critical and conceptual understanding of fundamental constants and their interpretive limits.

In this way, the work reinforces that the search for connections between mathematics and physics is also a search for understanding how we think about the universe. By recognizing the creative role of scientific imagination, we open space for new interpretations, new metaphors, and perhaps new ways of relating the ideal world of mathematical forms to the sensible world of experience. Whether the universe is or is not a product of human imagination remains an open

question, but it is precisely in this interval between the real and the conceptual that scientific investigation flourishes.

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